

Salts of Metal Ions with Organic Arsonic Acids. Part XI. Salts of Mn(II), Fe(III) and Zn(II) with Arylarsonic Acids.

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Salts of arylarsonic acids with manganese(II), iron(II) and zinc(II) having general formula : $(X.C_6H_4AsO_3)_m M.nH_2O$, have been prepared. Here, when $M=Mn(II)$, $m=1$ and $n=0, 0.5$ or 1 ; when $M=Fe(III)$, $m=1.5$ and $n=3$ or 4 and when $M=Zn(II)$, $m=1$ and $n=0, 0.5$ or 2 and $X=H, p-CH_3, p-Cl, p-Br, p-OCH_3, o-OCH_3, o-COOH$ or $o-NO_2$. Manganese(II) and iron(III) salts show the presence of metal metal interaction. Polymeric distorted octahedral structure is proposed for the salts.

COMPLEXES of zinc(II) with methylarsonic acid¹, *o*-amino-phenylarsonic acid² and phenylarsonic acid³ have been isolated but no work has been reported on compounds of manganese(II) and iron(III) with arylarsonic acids. In continuation of our studies on arylarsonic acids⁸⁻¹¹, the isolation of salts of manganese(II), iron(III) and zinc(II) with phenylarsonic acid (A), *p*-methyl-phenylarsonic acid (B), *p*-chloro-phenylarsonic acid (C), *p*-bromo-phenylarsonic acid (D), *p*-methoxyphenylarsonic acid (E), *o*-methoxyphenylarsonic acid (F), *o*-carboxyphenylarsonic acid (G) and *o*-nitrophenylarsonic acid (H) is being reported here. The salts were characterised by elemental analysis, magnetic susceptibilities IR and reflectance spectral studies.

Experimental

The arylarsonic acids were prepared by the reported methods.^{12, 13} The salts of manganese(II) were prepared by refluxing the alcoholic solutions of manganese(II) acetate (0.010 mole) and arylarsonic acid (0.011 mole) for about half an hour, when precipitate separated. The salts of iron(III) and zinc(II) were prepared in a similar manner using ferric ammonium sulphate and zinc acetate respectively. The salts were purified by washing the precipitate repeatedly with alcohol and drying under vacuum.

The estimation of carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and halogens was carried out by Australian Microanalytical Service, Melbourne. Manganese and iron were estimated gravimetrically as Mn_2O_7 and Fe_2O_3 , Zinc was determined volumetrically by EDTA titration.

The magnetic measurements were made at room temperature using Gouy method. The diamagnetic corrections were calculated on the basis of Pascal's constants¹⁴.

The IR spectra of arylarsonic acids and their salts were obtained as Nujol mulls on a Hilger and Watts H.800 Spectrophotometer ($4000-650\text{ cm}^{-1}$) using sodium chloride optics. The electronic spectra of the salts (with and/or without dilution with freshly prepared magnesium oxide) were recorded with the help of a Unicam Sp 700 A UV and visible Spectrophotometer having SP 735 diffuse reflectance attachment ($50,000-4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$).

Results and Discussion

On the basis of results of elemental analysis (Table 1) the arylarsonates may be represented by the general formula : $(X.C_6H_4AsO_3)_m M.nH_2O$. Here, when $M=Mn(II)$, $m=1$ and $n=0, 0.5$ or 1 ; when $M=Fe(III)$, $m=1.5$ and $n=3$ or 4 and when $M=Zn(II)$, $m=1$ and $n=0, 0.5$ or 2 . Due to high melting points and insolubility in common organic solvents of these salts, which are indicative of a polymeric nature, the measurements of conductivity and determination of molecular weights could not be carried out.

The various bands due to arsono group in the IR spectra of arylarsonic acids have been assigned as follows : ν_{OH} groups : 2750 and 2750 cm^{-1} ; As-C aromatic ; $1125-1077\text{ cm}^{-1}$ As=O : $935-845\text{ cm}^{-1}$ lit splits into a doublet in acids (B), (C) and (D) : As $\langle \nu$ asymmetric : $860-785\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and As $\langle \nu$ symmetric : $790-755\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The bands due to -OH groups are not observed in the spectra of the salts thus confirming the dibasic nature of the acids in these salts that had been indicated by the elemental analysis. The above conclusion is corroborated by the shifts in the positions of symmetric and asymmetric stretching frequencies of As $\langle \nu$ group of the acids on salt formation. Though in some of the salts, the shifts in the positions of symmetric and asymmetric bands are clearly visible, in others

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TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF THE SALTS.

S. No.	Salt	Calculated (%)			Found (%)			M**	X*	M**	μ_{eff} (B. M.)
		C	H	X*	C	H	X*				
1.	$C_6H_6ASO_3Mn$	28.24	1.96	—	28.45	2.25	—	21.4	—	21.4	4.31
2.	$p-CH_3C_6H_4ASO_3Mn$	31.23	2.60	—	31.89	2.90	—	20.2	—	20.2	4.10
3.	$p-ClC_6H_4ASO_3Mn \cdot 1/2H_2O$	24.12	1.68	11.90	23.97	2.23	12.40	18.2	12.40	18.2	4.19
4.	$p-BrC_6H_4ASO_3Mn$	21.56	1.19	23.95	21.29	1.45	24.10	16.4	24.10	16.4	4.20
5.	$p-OCH_3C_6H_4ASO_3Mn$	29.47	2.46	—	29.74	2.56	—	19.1	—	19.1	4.21
6.	$o-OCH_3C_6H_4ASO_3 \cdot Mn \cdot H_2O$	27.72	2.97	—	27.88	3.14	—	18.1	—	18.1	5.35
7.	$o-COOH \cdot C_6H_4ASO_3 \cdot Mn \cdot H_2O$	26.41	2.20	—	26.75	2.76	—	17.0	—	17.0	5.87
8.	$o-NO_2C_6H_4ASO_3 \cdot Mn \cdot H_2O$	22.64	1.89	4.37	22.73	1.95	4.23	17.0	4.23	17.0	5.50
9.	$(C_6H_5ASO_3)_2 \cdot Fe \cdot 3H_2O$	26.34	3.29	—	26.17	2.51	—	13.4	—	13.4	4.94
10.	$(p-CH_3C_6H_4ASO_3)_2 \cdot Fe \cdot 4H_2O$	28.06	4.12	—	27.41	3.23	—	12.4	—	12.4	5.44
11.	$(p-ClC_6H_4ASO_3)_2 \cdot Fe \cdot 4H_2O$	22.51	2.91	11.10	22.07	2.26	11.40	11.4	11.40	11.4	5.39
12.	$(p-OCH_3C_6H_4ASO_3)_2 \cdot Fe \cdot 3H_2O$	27.69	3.69	—	27.25	3.03	—	12.1	—	12.1	5.31
13.	$(o-NO_2C_6H_4ASO_3)_2 \cdot Fe \cdot 4H_2O$	21.79	2.82	4.24	20.40	1.75	4.62	11.0	4.62	11.0	4.26
14.	$p-CH_3C_6H_4ASO_3 \cdot Zn$	30.10	2.51	—	30.24	2.65	—	23.4	—	23.4	
15.	$p-ClC_6H_4ASO_3 \cdot Zn$	24.01	1.34	11.84	24.29	1.49	12.49	21.6	12.49	21.6	
16.	$p-BrC_6H_4ASO_3 \cdot Zn$	20.90	1.16	23.1	21.00	1.58	22.9	19.0	22.9	19.0	
17.	$p-OCH_3C_6H_4ASO_3 \cdot Zn$	28.44	2.37	—	28.47	2.32	—	22.1	—	22.1	
18.	$o-OCH_3C_6H_4ASO_3 \cdot Zn \cdot 1/2H_2O$	27.59	2.63	—	27.62	2.83	—	21.4	—	21.4	
19.	$o-COOH \cdot C_6H_4ASO_3 \cdot Zn \cdot 2H_2O$	24.35	2.61	—	24.85	2.83	—	18.7	—	18.7	
20.	$o-NO_2C_6H_4ASO_3 \cdot Zn$	23.19	1.29	4.51	23.36	1.38	4.24	21.0	4.24	21.0	

*X = Cl, Br or N

**M = Mn Fe or Zn.

the shifted bands overlap with each other or with the phenyl ring bands or with the bands due to As=O. In the salts of manganese (II), except o-carboxyphenylarsonate, in iron (III) salts with acids (A), (C) and (H) and zinc(II) salts with acids (B), (F) and (H), the As=O bands clearly shift downward by 10-100 cm^{-1} . In salts of iron(III) with acids (B) and (E), the As=O bands, instead of shifting downward, shifted upward by 45 cm^{-1} and cm^{-1} respectively. In other salts, the downward shifted (10-120 cm^{-1}) As=O bands overlap either with asymmetric stretch of $\text{As}=\overset{\ominus}{\text{O}}$ or with the band due to phenyl ring. The downward shift may be ascribed to the bonding of metal ions to As=O oxygen. The upward shift in As=O bands on formation of salt may be due to coupling of arsenic-oxygen and metal-oxygen oscillators. A small change in the position of As-C_{aromatic} stretch on salt formation also supports the above conclusion of coordination of As=O oxygen with metal ions in these salts.

In the spectrum of o-carboxy-phenylarsonic acid the bands at 3100, 14.0 and 1300 cm^{-1} may be assigned¹⁸ to -OH stretch, -O-H deformation and C-O stretch respectively. The elemental analysis suggests that the proton of -COOH group is not removed in the salts of o-carboxy-phenylarsonic acid. This is supported by the presence of bands due to -C-O-H group at almost same positions in the spectra of acid and salts. The doublet present at 1650, 1637 cm^{-1} due to C=O in the acid shifts to 1600, 1550 cm^{-1} in the zinc (II) salts, indicating coordination of C=O oxygen with zinc ion. The small change in the position of bands of substituted groups of the acids in salts may be due to change in the environment.

The room temperature magnetic moment values (4.10-5.50 B.M.) of Mn (II) and Fe (III) salts, except for manganese (II) o-carboxyphenylarsonate, are lower than the spin only value for five unpaired electrons. This fall may be ascribed to metal-metal interaction in the salts. The relatively higher magnetic moment values for Mn (II) salts of para-substituted-phenylarsonic acids than those for the salts of ortho-substituted acids may be explained on the basis of steric hinderance. The electronic reflectance spectra of Mn(II) salts show two d-d bands, one around 23,800 cm^{-1} and another broad band in the region 18,500-17,300 cm^{-1} , and charge transfer bands above 35,000 cm^{-1} . The corresponding bands in Fe(III) salts appear at 22,500 cm^{-1} in the region 12,350-11,600 cm^{-1} and above 30,000 cm^{-1} . The two d-d bands in these salts may be assigned¹⁹ as

${}^4A_{1g}(G), {}^4E_g(G) \leftarrow {}^6A_{1g}$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(G), {}^4T_{2g}(G) \leftarrow {}^6A_{1g}$. On the basis of polymeric nature and abovementioned studies, a distorted octahedral structure is proposed for these salts.

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